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- ✓ ANIQ FANLAR
- ✓ TABIIY FANLAR
- ✓ SIYOSIY FANLAR
- ✓ IJTIMOIIY FANLAR

- ✓ IQTISOD FANLARI
- ✓ TEXNIKA FANLARI
- ✓ TIBBIYOT FANLARI
- ✓ PEDAGOGIKA FANLARI

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DEVELOPMENT AND USAGE OF RELIGIOUS TERMINOLOGY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation: *This thesis analyses the derivation and development of religious vocabulary in English language based on the dictionaries and literary works. It also illustrates some of the semantic types of religious lexicon.*

Keywords: *religious vocabulary, theology, exotic lexicon, imam, sheikh, semantic groups.*

РАЗВИТИЕ И ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ РЕЛИГИОЗНОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

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Аннотация: *В данной диссертационной работе анализируется возникновение и развитие религиозной лексики в английском языке на основе словарей и литературных произведений. Также иллюстрируются некоторые семантические типы религиозной лексики.*

Ключевые слова: *религиозная лексика, теология, экзотическая лексика, имам, шейх, семантические группы.*

From the point of view of linguistics language is the basic tool for understanding any religion. Our use of language can tell our listener or reader a great deal about ourselves – in particular, about our regional origins, social background, level of education, occupation, age, sex, and personality. A major function of language is the expression of personal identity. Language has been one of the main means to portray a religion. Of course other means such as religious customs, symbols and chants have been used. However for a religion to survive among the coming generations, it has to be communicated and this is where language plays its role. For many years language has been a major key to study and research the religion, to learn the holy books and fully understand and comment the core of those books people have to know the language that those books were written in. In Islam, Muslims have paid a great attention to the study

and analysis of the Arabic language as they developed linguistic studies for the purpose of Qur'anic recitations⁴. Arabic is the language of worship of all Muslim nations from the fact that it is a language, from the fact that the religious traditions are from Arabic, Persian, Uzbek and other languages regardless, they are considered the professional vocabulary of the Uzbek language to the issue of "prayer, fasting, zakat, call to prayer, hajj, marriage, funeral, taraweh, Friday, Eid prayers or in general, prayers such as sermons, recitations, religious meetings performed on the basis of Arabic text, verses and prayers. These processes are primarily religious from the point of view that it requires knowledge of terms and their correct application approaches. At the centre of all the world's main religions lies a body of sacred writing, revered by believers. Literacy is often introduced into community by the spread of a religion through publications of sacred books and their translations. During the Middle Ages and the Renaissance, English speakers came into contact with the prestigious intellectual centers of the Arab world. This contact led to a flow of borrowings from Arabic into English. English is very rich in borrowed words from many other languages for religious purposes. As stated above the influence of Islam into English language are closely associated with the muslims who study the Islam and Qur'an in English. As a result, many words are taken into English. Adam Brown in his paper *The Treatment of Religious Terminology in English Dictionaries*, occupied himself with aspects of the treatment of various Islamic and Christian terms in the English language dictionaries: Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English, Collins Cobuild English Dictionary and Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary and Cambridge International Dictionary of English⁵. Here we can see some of the Arabic words which come in the English dictionaries such as Longman, Oxford, Cobuild and Cambridge: *haj, halal, Shia, Sunni, oyatallah, imam hijab, kibra, Mecca*. Many terms which have religious meaning in English are the arabic words that belonged to Quran. Most of the religious words existed in English derived from Holy books of different religions.

Here are some of the semantic groups of religious lexemes in English:

1. The name of the Creator in different versions: God, Allah, Rabbi. These names have the same meaning which appreciates the unique creator in all religions.
2. Names of people in relation to their faith: Muslim, the Christian,

⁴Belinda M.B. Surjeet S, Masdini H The Relationship Between Language and Religion International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences: Vol. 10 , No. 11, 2020

⁵ Dazdarević Samina Univerzitet u Novom Pazaru. Religious terminology in the english language Applied Linguistics Today, ALT 4. "Izazovi modernog doba", Philological Faculty of Belgrade, 2012

3. Mumin, believer, orthodox.
4. Names denoting religious ranks: Prophet, abbot, apostle, pope, imam, sheikh.
5. Names of angels: Gabriel, Michael, Jabraail, Mikoil, Munkir, Nakir.
6. Words denoting the designation of religious rituals: hajj, baptism, hanta.
7. Names of religious holidays: the day of Ashura, the New Year for Hijri, Easter, Christmas, Ramadan Hayit.
8. Names of buildings and structures of cult and ritual purpose and their parts:
9. Mazar Arab, grave, cemetery, minara, 'mosque', 'church', monastery etc .
10. The names of the religious texts and teachings are: Koran, Old Testament, Bible, Tawrot.
11. Names of religious clothing: hijab, vestment, burka.
12. Religious dogmas, religious organizations and associations. To this group we have included all the lexemes associated with religious trends, currents, their teachings: Brahmanism, Islam, Christianity, Atheism, Catholicism⁶.
13. Names of things and objects used in religious ceremonies: prayer mat, rosary, Quran book, shroud, icon, candle, cross etc. in Uzbek language prayer beads, prayer mat, frock, icon.

Religious language is so removed from everyday conversation as to be almost unintelligible, except to an initiated minority. Religion itself is often emotive, lofty, serious and spiritual, not addressing the mundane but the grand. Its language therefore reveals grave, sober, solemn, serious and spiritual discourse.

The text in the original language is a restriction on one's choice of English which does not normally apply to other varieties. It is obvious that English language has variety of religious vocabulary lexicon which comprises the features of Christianity and Islam. It is systematically observed that translation of words from English into another language which have religious meaning are managed by using different ways other than direct translation. Moreover, the influence of Arabic language which served to study and comment the holy sources of Islam can still be seen in English vocabulary⁷. It is clearly seen that the Arabic words in

⁶ Abdullina G.R., Doctor of Philology The Turkish Online Journal of Design, Art and Communication - TOJDAC ISSN: 2146-5193, September 2018 Special Edition, p.1872-1879

⁷ Khodjakulova F. Lexico-Semantic Features of Religious Terms Senior teacher of International Islamic academy of Uzbekistan Euroasian research bulletin

English have religious meaning and included to the religious terminology of English lexicon.

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